

ACTIVITY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF INFORMATION SECURITY IN THE MECHANISMS OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITY OF ENTERPRISES OF THE ENERGY INDUSTRY

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Today, it is impossible to imagine without information and information technology. As the importance of information technologies in not only improving but also developing the way of life of mankind is increasing, the main structure of innovative activities began to be implemented in the scope of information technologies. As a result of the automation of technological tools, machines, equipment based on information technologies, the complexity of algorithms has stimulated a sharp increase in innovative information technologies.

The importance of the energy industry in the industrial infrastructure of every country is extremely high, and its operation in harmony with information technologies has become an urgent requirement of the 21st century. In the energy industry, the dependence of information technology on extreme digitization has led to the development of cyber security. This, in turn, requires consideration of the effectiveness and efficiency of information security in the mechanisms of organizational and economic activity of energy industry enterprises.

The history of information security is related to hackers, and the first cyber attack was recorded in 1834 in France when information about financial markets was intercepted through a telegraph line. There are many cases of such cyber attacks on telephone and telegraph systems, which were carried out by Rene Carmil in 1940. He worked as an experienced master of punch-card computers, used his invention to process information, and officially founded hacking through the idea of finding other similar users. In 1962, scientists at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology installed the first keyword input on a computer, after the stock exchanges for working with basic economic and financial information became more and more popular. In this context, the economic foundations of cyber security emerged.

The economy of cyber security is not clearly defined, and cyber security and the economy are explained separately. Specifically, Wikipedia refers to economic cyber security as “the economics of information security refers to the economics of privacy and computer security. The economics of information

security includes strictly rational "homo economicus" models and behavioral economics.

Information security as a science was included in the nanoeconomy after 2010. In 2000, R. Anderson, a technical professor at the Cambridge Information Laboratory of Great Britain, stated that the main problem of developing security technologies is the alignment of incentives for technology. With this, R. Anderson emphasized the need to ensure the integration of economic ideas with technical projects. According to him, the risks that threaten economic security should be eliminated by investing in technologies that provide it. The activation of the mechanism of this situation is guaranteed to justify itself at least socially in terms of ensuring the lifestyle and well-being of the population.

In 2000, Harvard Kemp, an economic researcher at the Wolfram School of Public Administration's Faculty of Economics, commented that "security is not a guarantee of mutual well-being, on the contrary, every value has its weak points according to the interaction of feedback" in relation to the definition of problematic and problematic aspects of Internet browsers used in the popularization of the Internet. In particular, the fact that the information of Mozilla Internet browsers was easily allowed to be hacked by entry-level experts was realized thanks to the fact that this security was implemented through the tools of mass users. Also, in the booklet published by L. Gordon and P. Martin entitled "Responding to competitors' analytical system through information security", they emphasized the importance of using confidential information to gain an advantage for competing companies. According to them, the development of an information security mechanism aimed at preventing the use of information ownership in exploiting the subtleties of a competitor in the market is considered capable of ensuring that the sole owner of the information infrastructure is the enterprise. This conclusion was formed based on calculations with a structure based on the theory of games.

In 2001, Carnegie Mellon University developed a hierarchical holographic model through a proposal to develop a risk assessment mechanism aimed at alternative use of computer emergency services. With its help, they founded the instrument that ensures the safety of the initial multilateral investment management using risks. Accordingly, for the first time at the "OCTAVE" enterprise, a systematic mechanized complex was developed by the US company "CERT" for the purpose of investment risk management. Based on this, eliminating the risks of investment projects has become the main standard criterion for ensuring information security.

In our opinion, the economy of information security is understood as an economy based on the prevention of economic harm from the means of each information technology user. Its main activity is economic and financial support of information security.

Cybersecurity in the energy industry has required a more focused approach based on the development of Internet tools. In the prevention of illegal ways of using energy resources, it is not enough that the algorithms of digital technologies can show the exact time and location of the attack, but also it is determined by its attitude to prevent the occurrence of emergency situations. The use of information technologies in the energy industry began in the 1970s, and was initially associated with the popularization of free implementation of technological tools. At the international economic forum of Davos, the information security of energy companies ranks 5th among the major global risks. In particular, in 1989, in the USA, using the Joseph Pop program, Robert Morris organized an attack for the first time by placing a special code on disks to extort money in exchange for a partial loss of money in the bank. Also, in 2019, the US company "Capital One" managed to hack more than 100 million customers' personal account numbers, insurance, social security, bank account numbers, credit rating and similar important and confidential information by P. Thompson. From this, the financial loss of energy enterprises is 72 billion. Estimated in US dollars. The Internet is considered to be the main threat to information security. Other information security tools do not have code and do not have the ability to execute software commands. Accordingly, using the Internet, as beneficial as it may be, can also present its own risks.

References:

1. Пунам Патил. Эффективный метод кибербезопасности: Защита данных от киберпреступников (русское издание). Scienza Scripts. 2022 г, 76 стр.
2. Ахмет Эфе. Организационная кибербезопасность: позиция
3. ИТ-аудита, основанного на экономическом риске, теоретических и практических аспектах кибербезопасности (русское издание). 2023 г, 452 стр.
4. Lawrence A. Gordon and Martin P. Loeb. Using Information Security as a Response to Competitor "ANALYSIS SYSTEMS". COMMUNICATIONS OF THE ACM. September 2001/Vol. 44, No. 9, 71-77.
5. Гордон, Лоуренс А. ; Леб, Мартин П. (ноябрь 2002 г.). «Экономика инвестиций в информационную безопасность» . Транзакции ACM по

информационной и системной безопасности . 5 (4): 438–457. дои :
10.1145/581271.581274 .S2CID 1500788 .

6. Ross Anderson. Why Information Security is Hard – An Economic Perspective. University of Cambridge Computer Laboratory, J. Thomson Avenue, Cambridge CB3 0FD, UK Ross.Anderson@cl.cam.ac.uk, 2000, 64 p.

7. <https://www.monroecollege.edu/news/cybersecurity-history-hacking-data-breaches#:~:text=Cybersecurity%20history%20is%20interesting%20indeed,would%20become%20%E2%80%9Cthe%20internet.%E2%80%9D>.

